

Sample Name: ctDNA-H 75x

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                               Seq. Line :    1
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                          Location  :    1
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 5:07:12 PM              Inj       :    1
                                                    Inj Volume: 50.000 µl

Sequence File   : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                  17-06-08\dNMP to dNTP yield.S
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                  17-06-08\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 5:05:53 PM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

Fraction List

Frac #	Well #	Location	Volume [µl]	BeginTime [min]	EndTime [min]	Reason	Mass
1	1	32	250.20	3.500	4.001	Time	
2	1	33	247.26	4.006	4.500	Time	
3	1	34	246.85	4.507	5.000	Time	
4	1	35	247.73	5.006	5.500	Time	
5	1	36	247.52	5.505	6.000	Time	
6	1	37	247.11	6.006	6.500	Time	
7	1	38	247.27	6.506	7.000	Time	
8	1	39	246.70	7.007	7.500	Time	
9	1	40	246.23	7.508	8.000	Time	
10	1	41	112.73	8.017	8.243	Time	

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                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
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                  17-06-08\dNMP to dNTP yield.S
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                  17-06-08\DNTF QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 5:05:53 PM by SYSTEM
=====
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=====
                          Area Percent Report
=====
```

```
Sorted By           :      Signal
Multiplier          :      1.0000
Dilution           :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	2.142	VB R	0.1493	105.59324	9.89389	8.1321
2	4.098	BV R	0.0872	159.58893	27.85511	12.2905
3	5.310	BV	0.0974	357.42453	57.38073	27.5266
4	5.679	VB	0.1015	227.58215	34.60863	17.5269
5	8.032	BB	0.1266	448.28299	54.45256	34.5239

```
Totals :                      1298.47184  184.19093
```

```
=====
*** End of Report ***
```